

INFLUENCE OF LAMINATE SURFACE RESIN DEPTH ON THE INTERFACE STRENGTH OF OVERMOULDED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A systematic study was performed to investigate the influence of surface resin depth on the interfacial strength of overmoulded composites using both experimental and simulation methods. Discontinuous fibre reinforced polyetheretherketone (PEEK) was injected over a unidirectional (UD) laminate to manufacture lap-shear specimens, varying both the surface resin depth present on the laminate insert and the weight fraction of discontinuous fibres filling the injected polymer. The surface resin depth was modified from a standard quasi-isotropic laminate with limited surface resin content with inclusion of a film of two different polymers. This included both polyaryletherketone (LMPAEK) and polyetherimide (PEI) film of thickness 40µm. In both cases the films were added to the laminate surface during the consolidation of the laminate. Mechanical tests showed an increase in lap-shear strength when a thin film was present on the specimen surface. A similar improvement in bond strength was achieved for both LMPAEK and PEI surface film layers. A counterpart numerical modelling process was developed to understand the heat transfer process occurring during overmoulding. The primary finding of the simulation was that a reduction in local thermal diffusivity at the interface (such as achieved through a resin-rich layer at the interface) can be used to increase the interface temperature. The results of this study are important for the manufacture of overmoulded composites as both the technical findings and the simulation process presented can be used in the design process to improve interface strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite injection overmoulding is performed by combining injection moulding with the use of continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites (also referred to as the insert or substrate throughout this text) by placement within a mould tool prior to the injection stage. As the molten polymer is injected into the mould, contact with the surface of the insert allows a bond to form and consolidate under pressure, heat, and time. Composite injection overmoulding can reduce the costs associated with the manufacture of complex composite structures. This is the case, as incorporating injection moulding for features can significantly reduce processing times and increase automation. The superior strength of continuous fibre reinforcement can be attained for load-bearing components by incorporation of a composite insert [1]. However, achieving a desired interface strength may be an issue as the formation of a strong bond at the interface is required for maintaining structural integrity in load-bearing applications. The interface strength is dependent on the material and processing conditions which include (but are not limited to) interface temperature, crystallinity, thermodynamic compatibility, and local flow velocity [2-5].

2 METHODOLOGY

During this study a systematic approach was undertaken to understand the relationship between the resin present on the surface of a composite laminate and the interface strength of overmoulded composites. This involved the manufacture and testing of overmoulded single lap-shear specimens alongside the development of a complimentary overmoulding process simulation to understand the heat transfer process (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Overmoulding mould used for the manufacture of overmoulded coupons (left) and simulation grid of counterpart process simulation.

2.1 Overmoulding single lap-shear specimens

Rectangular coupons were prepared using quasi-isotropic Toray Cetex TC1225 composite reinforced with T300 carbon fibres. The matrix of the TC1225 composite is a proprietary blend of thermoplastic polymers from the polyaryletherketone (PAEK) family which are selected to reduce its melting point in order to improve processing, particularly for thermal bonding scenarios and is referred to by its suppliers as low-melt PAEK (LMPAEK). To make a comparison between the bond properties of laminates which had a higher surface resin fraction, additional LMPAEK laminates were obtained from Toray which included an additional preconsolidated film on the surface. One side of the surface-resin modified LMPAEK composite was consolidate with an additional LMPAEK film while the other side had a polyethylenimine (PEI) film. This allowed inserts to be flipped to vary whether insert/injected melt interface was on the LMPAEK or PEI side of the laminate. Two different grades of injected material were used to manufacture overmoulded lap-shear specimens. These were two different grades of polyetheretherketone (PEEK) which contained different concentrations of discontinuous reinforced carbon fibres. The two grades of material were Evonik's Vestakeep 2000 CF30 (30wt% carbon) and Vestakeep 4000 CF10 (10wt% carbon) and are abbreviated as V2000 CF30, and V4000 CF10 throughout this work. These two grades of material contain PEEK of a different range of molecular

weights, with V2000 being lower than V4000. PEEK is a polymer within the greater PAEK family and as such highly compatible with both PEI and LMPAEK.

Overmoulding was performed using an Arburg Allrounder 520 S injection moulding machine. The mould block was cooled by pressurised water and produced rectangular coupons of dimensions 144 x 20 mm. Lap-shear specimens were manufactured from the overmoulded bi-material specimens by milling a channel on either side of the specimen, allowing a one-inch overlap about its centre.

2.1 Simulation of the overmoulding process

The overmoulding process was simulated using the Volume of Fluid (VoF) method in the simulation package Ansys Fluent. The following continuity equation is solved for each phase of index i . The continuous phase is denoted by the subscript 1 [6]:

$$\frac{1}{\rho_1} \left[\frac{\delta}{\delta t} (\alpha_i \rho_i) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_i \rho_i \vec{u}) \right] = S_{\rho,i} \quad (1)$$

where ρ is density, t is time in seconds, α is the volume fraction, \vec{u} is the velocity vector. $S_{\rho,i}$ is a density sink term used to return the air pressure to ambient within an enclosed mould. The momentum conservation equation is calculated for a shared velocity field with volume-averaged properties [6]:

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta t} (\rho \vec{u}) + \nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{u} \vec{u}) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \bar{\tau} + S_{mo,i} \quad (2)$$

where p is pressure, $\bar{\tau}$ is the stress vector and $S_{mo,i}$ is the component i of the momentum source term to balance the momentum equation based on the extracted air. The energy equation is calculated for a shared field:

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta t} (\rho E) + \nabla \cdot (\vec{u} (\rho E + p)) = \nabla \cdot (k \nabla T + (\bar{\tau} \cdot \vec{u})) + S_E \quad (3)$$

E is the energy contained within a cell, k is thermal conductivity, T is temperature. S_E balances the energy equation for the extracted continuous phase for the shared energy field, similar way to S_{mo} .

Separate material properties are implemented for the composite substrate and the polymer film layer at the insert surface, allowing their relative influence on the heat transfer process to be captured. Figure 2 shows the layers of material used in the insert region of the simulation of heat transfer during the overmoulding process.

Figure 2: Diagram of the composite thermal domain (left) are shown next to micrographs (right) used to determine dimensions. Images are extracted such that the flow direction is normal to the plane of observation.

For solid composite regions an estimation of specific heat capacity, density, and thermal conductivity was required to compute the heat flux. The rule of mixtures in either the series (Voigt Model) or parallel form (Reuss Model) were used in each of the layers of the composite insert, considering their orientation. As there is a continuous path of fibres to transfer heat, the thermal conductivity in the fibre direction was calculated through the Voigt model (Eq. 4) in addition to all scalar material properties. In the transverse directions, the fibre material is discontinuous and insulated by the matrix material. In this case, the homogenised thermal conductivity is typically closer to its theoretical minimum and the Reuss Model (Eq. 5) offers a better estimation [7].

The Voigt model was implemented for thermal conductivity in the longitudinal direction of the fibres as well as for all scalar properties:

$$P_c = P_f V_f + P_m (1 - V_f) \quad (4)$$

where P represents a generic material property. The subscript c denotes the property relating to the composite whereas f and m relate to its fibre and matrix constituents, respectively. V_f is the fibre volume fraction. The rule of mixtures was applied in the parallel form (Reuss model) to model thermal conductivity in the transverse and vertical directions relative to fibre alignment:

$$\frac{1}{P_c} = \frac{1}{P_f} V_f + \frac{1}{P_m} (1 - V_f) \quad (5)$$

The thermal properties of carbon fibre were extracted from the Toray T300 datasheet. Polymer thermal properties were sourced from the Moldflow database.

3 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The results of the single lap-shear tests are displayed in Table 1 where they are referred to by their injected material and, where applicable, the presence of a surface film layer is denoted by the brackets. For both injected PEEK grades, the lap-shear strength is improved considerably with the consolidated surface film when compared to the unmodified laminate. Generally, the mean values of lap-shear strength are higher for the 30% carbon fibre loaded injected PEEK overall. However, considerable variation in results are noted for some material configurations, notably the V2000 CF30 (unmodified) and V4000 CF10 with LMPAEK film. However, the material configurations with a PEI film interface generally defies this rule as the lap-shear strength is marginally higher at the lower injected melt fibre concentration. The PEI film also performs marginally better than the LMPAEK surface film, with both higher lap-shear strength and low standard deviation for both injected melt configurations.

Specimen	Lap-shear strength (MPa)
V2000 CF30	9.7 \mp 4.5
V2000 CF30 (PEI)	16.8 \mp 0.9
V2000 CF30 (LMPAEK)	15.2 \mp 0.2
V4000 CF10	7.9 \mp 1.4
V4000 CF10 (PEI)	18.6 \mp 0.7
V4000 CF10 (LMPAEK)	14.4 \mp 2.4

Table 1: Interface strength as measured by single lap-shear tests for all specimen configurations.

The strength of thermally bonded thermoplastic interfaces is known to be closely related to the temperature of the interface and welding time. A spatial dependence on temperature is observed in Figure 3 which occurs due to the variation in time of contact of the injected melt flow with the substrate. In all configurations a significantly higher interface temperature is observed in a localised region near the injection gate due to longer contact time.

The interface temperature after the pressure/velocity switch-over is substantially higher for all configurations when comparing the those with an applied surface film to those which have no film present on the surface. The primary mechanism responsible for this is the increase in the ability of the PEEK melt to transfer heat to the interface (thermal effusivity) at higher carbon fibre concentrations due to an increase in thermal conductivity. Since the time for bonding of thermoplastic polymers through ‘interdiffusion’ is closely related to temperature and time, and is the primary mechanism responsible for interface formation, an increase in interface temperature is likely to be the primary cause of the increase in lap-shear strength in all film configurations results when compared to the unmodified laminate with low surface resin depth present. A higher CF concentration within the injected polymer also results in a comparably higher interface temperature due to an increased thermal effusivity of the phase which allows heat to be exchanged more easily from the injected melt to the interface.

Figure 3: Contours of interface temperature during simulation of the overmoulding process, recorded at the pressure-velocity switch-over.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Overall, it was demonstrated that the interface strength can be improved through the modification of the local thermal diffusivity in the vicinity of the interface. In the case of unidirectional fibre reinforcement, a high volume fraction of carbon fibres may provide useful mechanical properties but at the cost of a high thermal diffusivity. A high thermal diffusivity can prevent the development of a strong interface by increasing the energy flux through the insert and away from the interface where a high temperature promotes the formation of a strong bond. Through a relatively minor surface modification, the local diffusivity at the interface is improved, resulting in the development of a strong bond. Modification of the surface resin depth in this case improves the interfacial bond strength without altering the laminate reinforcement. The results of this study are useful for the design of overmoulded structures. This is especially the case for those which require a high volume fraction of carbon fibres such as in load-bearing structures. The simulation process developed is also useful for this purpose and could be used to optimise the surface resin depth of the composite for both insert composite strength and interface strength of the overmoulded composite.

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